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of **EXPRESSION**

A Creative Folio

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Rookie At Work

Starting a new job is scary,
Especially with no experience.
In hospitality, not everyone gets orientation;
Some are thrown straight into the rush.

Mistakes aren't allowed,
Some coworkers help, others don't.
Rookies get the hardest tasks,
Clearing plates, wiping tables,
And working odd schedules.

It's tiring and overwhelming,
But once you find your rhythm,
You start to appreciate the grind,
Because that's where growth begins.